

(Assessment of Parents Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement ... Suleiman, S. O. Et al., 2025)

Assessment of Parents' Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement among Secondary School Students in Niger State, Nigeria.

SULEIMAN, Suleiman Chado (Ph.D.)¹

E mail: suleimansuleiman7@gmail.com
+234(0)8065556073

ONONAIWU, A. Ijoma¹

E mail: agnesononaiwu60@gmail.com
+234(0)805582029

AMINU, Sani²

E mail: aminusani1976@gmail.com
+234(0)7030794152

¹Department of Counselling Psychology Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida University, Lapai Nigeria

²Department of Sociology, Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida University, Lapai Nigeria

Abstract

The study investigated Parents socio-economic status as a factor on Academic Achievement of secondary schools in Niger State, Nigeria. The study looked at effects of parents' socio-economic status on academic achievement of students' secondary schools. The study used ex-post factor method, in which groups with qualities that already existed are compared, in 150 schools with a population of (373,529) students, out of which 384 participants were drawn as sample size using multi stage technique. The instruments used include Kuppuswamy classification of socio-economic status and End of year examination scores tagged, (KCSESEYESQ). The instrument was pilot tested among 50 students in different location and the reliability of KCSESEYESQ was 0.81 obtained through test re-test method. To direct the course of investigation, six objectives, and questions were set to guide the study, six research hypotheses were also tested to guide the conduct of the study. T-test and ANOVA statistics were used to test the hypotheses, with a significant level of 0.05. The Findings revealed that parents' socio-economic status (finance) have a significant effect on the academic achievement of secondary schools students in Niger State. In conclusion, the findings indicated that parents 'income, educational background and occupational status all significantly affects students' academic achievement. Based on the findings, it was recommended that parents should support educational pursuits of their children financially, academically and experience wise, Government to employed qualified teachers and posted to teach in rural and urban areas, lastly scholarship assistance can be initiated to facilitate education among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Key words: Parents, Socio-economic status, students, Academic, Achievement

Introduction

Academic achievement of students remains an issue of great interest to educationists, psychologist and stakeholders, as it remains the means of distinguishing successful students from unsuccessful ones. It is a means of assessing the extent to which learning has taken place in students and is intended to improve their life and the nation at large. The issue of low academic achievement at the secondary level seeks for serious concern since it takes its origin from the lower level that is responsible for the training of both middle and high-level man-power for the country. Therefore, under-achievement at this level will be a disaster for the country. Presently, some employers of labour are already lamenting about the low quality of our undergraduates. Many now prefer graduates from foreign universities, such as Asia, UK, USA and neighboring African countries. In a study (Eyong, David and Umoh 2014), it was stated that there had been a reported incidence of under-achievement among students in secondary schools as evidenced by poor outing of WAEC results, which for years had been the standard measurement of academic achievement.

Despite these laudable efforts, it is unfortunate to find some students irrespective of their intelligent quotient (IQ) still considered under achievers. This indicates that the factors responsible for their under-academic achievement are due to teaching methodology, the nature of curriculum and the inability to cover the syllabus, among others. Therefore, there is the need to look at the factors related to students' psychosocial and cognitive attributes that may have some effects on their socio-economic status on academic achievement, since they are psychosocial beings.

The researcher deems this as an important vacuum to research into. A lot of factors have contributed to poor academic achievement of students. According to literatures academic achievement is a product of a number of factors operating within the individual and outside him. Broadly speaking, the main factor which influences academic achievement is the parents' socio-economic status. It can also be added that it has now been fairly established that the emotional factors, most particularly anxiety, environmental factors and levels of aspiration, largely determine one's academic achievement, which this study is not set out to investigate. A major factor that determines students' academic achievement is parents' socio-economic status.

(Assessment of Parents Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement ... Suleiman, S. O. Et al., 2025)

Socio-Economic Status (SES) According to American Psychological Association (APA), socio-economic status is commonly conceptualized as the social standing or class of an individual or group, and it is often measured as a combination of education, income and occupation. In the present study, a student SES is identified by the information provided by the questionnaire about the students' parents' academic and professional qualifications, income and occupational affiliations. Parental education and socio-economic supports are very important ingredients in students' academic achievement. The finding of studies has indicated that the academic achievement of students is contingent upon parents' socio-economic condition. For instance, Li and Qiu (2018) state that family socioeconomic status has a greater impact on the total effect of children's academic achievement. This means that parental socio-economic status is a vital factor that affects the academic achievement of students significantly. Studies have also shown that the academic achievement of students is directly proportional to parental income, education and occupation of their parent. Pant, (2020) in a study revealed that majority of students of low SES has poor academic achievement.

That is why it is right to say that the high socio-economic status of parents plays a fundamental and crucial role in the enhancement of children's academic achievement. So, differences have been observed between those students who come from different financial status and different parental educational levels. The students belonging to higher socio-economic backgrounds will achieve academically better than those with low socio-economic backgrounds. This is the general over-view of the majority, but the same assertion mostly is true as related studies pointed out those students who mostly come from deprived socio-economic and educational backgrounds achieve academically and relatively better than those coming from higher socio-economic and educational background. This trend or phenomena is referred to as educational elasticity.

Academic achievement refers to the outcome of education and the extent to which a student, teacher or institution has achieved the educational goals. It is commonly measured by examinations or continuous assessment. Academic achievement focuses on particular learning in a particular setting, which is defined by examination scores, teachers' grades and percentiles in academic subjects. School successes depend upon the ability of students to qualify in such examinations. For present study, academic achievement is defined as the cumulative grade obtained by students in the end of final examinations conducted by the schools during the year May/ June 2021/2022. This

(Assessment of Parents Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement ... Suleiman, S. O. Et al., 2025)

study is aimed at assessing the effects of parents' socio-economic status on academic achievement among the secondary school students in Niger state.

Socio-economic status (SES) is an economics and sociological combined total measure of a person's work experience and of an individual's or family's economic and social position in relation to others based on income, education and occupation. When analyzing a family's SES, the household income, earners' education and occupation are examined, as well as combined income, among individuals, when their own attributes are assessed. According to Mladenka, Ana, Ivana and Merima, (2017). Parental socio-economic status is a multidimensional concept of social importance for the growth and development, health outcomes and education of the children. Its definition generally refers to the amount of parental income, their employment status and level of education. Socio-economic status is typically broken into three categories (high SES, middle SES and low SES) to describe the three areas a family or an individual may fall into. When placing a family or an individual into one of these categories, any or all of the three variables (income, education and occupation) can be assessed (Saifi and Mehood, 2011).

Income refers to wages, salaries, profits, rents and any flow of earning received. It can also come in the form of unemployment or workers' compensation, social security, pensions, interests or dividends, royalties, trusts, alimony, or other government, public or family financial assistance. Income can be looked at in two terms, relative and absolute. Absolute income, as theorized by the economist John Maynard Keynes, is the relationship in which as income increases, so will consumption, but not at the same rate. Relative income dictates a person or family's savings and consumption based on the family's income in relation to others. Income was most strongly associated to all indicators; the association remained statistically significant when adjusting to other indicators. Alexander, Stefan and Ingemar (2017). Low income families focus on meeting immediate needs and do not accumulate wealth that could be passed on to future generations, thus increasing inequality. Families with higher and expendable income can accumulate wealth and focus on meeting immediate needs while being able to consume and enjoy luxuries and weather crises.

Researchers have claimed that the economic status of parents influences the academic achievement of the students. It was argued that parental economic status and education play a vital role in the learning achievement of their children. Parents of a

(Assessment of Parents Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement ... Suleiman, S. O. Et al., 2025)

medium socioeconomic class found to be more conscious about the future carrier of their children (Thomson, 2018)

Occupational prestige, as one component of SES, encompasses both income and educational attainment. Occupational status reflects the educational attainment required to obtain the job and income levels that vary with different jobs and within ranks of occupations. Additionally, it shows achievement in the skills required for the job. Occupational status measures social position by describing job characteristic, decision making ability and control and psychological demands on the job. Occupations are ranked by the census (among other organizations) and opinion polls from the general population are surveyed. Some of the most prestigious occupations are physicians and surgeons, lawyers, chemical and biomedical engineers, university professors and communications analysts. These jobs, considered to be grouped in the high SES

Classification, provide more challenging work and greater control over working conditions but require more ability. The job with lower rankings include food preparation workers, counter attendants, bartenders and helpers, dishwashers, janitors, maids and housekeepers, vehicle cleaners and parking lot attendants. The jobs that are less valued also offer significantly lower wages and often are more laborious, very hazardous and provide less autonomy. Occupation is the most difficult factor to measure because so many exist and there are so many competing scales. Many scales rank occupations based on the level of skill involved, from unskilled manual labor t professional or use a combined measure using the education level needed and the income involved (Afifa, Kusum, Anamika, Kamlesh and Manohar, 2015). From the above explanation, it can be interpreted that the majority of researchers agree that income, education and occupation together best represent SES, while some others feel that changes in family structure should also be considered. With the definition of SES more clearly defined, it is now important to discuss the effect of SES on students' cognitive abilities and academic success. Several researchers have found that SES affects students' stabilities.

Another important issues concerning students' socio-economic background is whether it is defined by the characteristics of their fatherism, their motherism or some combination of both. Traditionally, studies of the effects of social background on educational outcomes have measured social class or socio-economic status by father's occupation. This assumes that the class position of the family is determined by the

(Assessment of Parents Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement ... Suleiman, S. O. Et al., 2025)

occupation of the adult male and female occupation is largely irrelevant. Since the mid-1970s, the traditional view has come under attack from feminists, who argue, justifiably, that women's occupations are relevant to both their own social and economic position and that of their families. In the context of post-war years, the traditional procedure was more understandable. Men were viewed as 'the provider', 'the head of the house hold' or 'main breadwinner' and the proportion of married women in the work force was considerably lower than it is today. Given the present situation of high proportions of married women in the labour force, 'career women' and increasing numbers of house husband, the traditional procedure is less attractive than it once was (Amogne, 2015).

An important aspect of disadvantage is family structure. It is often believed that students living in one parent or blended families do less well at school than students from more traditional nuclear families. The detrimental effects of family disrupt found on the social mobility is most through education. There is little doubt that it is desirable to monitor differences in educational outcome between types of family structures. It is also true that the type of family a student comes from is relevant to the measurement of parental occupation and education. However, it is not clear if family structure comes under the rubrics of socio-economic background or is a distinct source of educational disadvantage (Chioma, Bernadethe and Joseph, 2017). The researchers, after studying the above literature on socio-economic status level, resolved to present the literature on academic achievement.

Statement of the Problem

It has been notice for quite some times the dwindling nature of student's academic of secondary school students in Niger State. This was attributed to daily poor academic among students overtime. There is therefore the need to nip this challenge at the bud before it becomes a source of serious concerned to both the state and the national at large. Academic achievement will be jeopardized because students cannot accomplish academic tasks, and had difficulty meeting educational and career goals. In the long run, there is the possibility of students dropping out from schools. Therefore, the present study precisely seeks to investigate under academic achievement against influence of parents' socio-economic status levels as a factor on academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

(Assessment of Parents Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement ... Suleiman, S. O. Et al., 2025)

The objective of this study includes the followings:

1. To ascertain whether parents' income affects high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
2. To evaluate effect of parents' educational background on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
3. To measure the parents' level of employment influence on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
4. To determine the difference between Parents' income and educational background on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
5. To determine the difference between Parents' educational background and level of employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
6. To determine the interactive effect of Parents' income, educational background and level of employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Research Questions

The following questions are raised:-

1. What are the effects of parents' income on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State?
2. What are the effects of parents' educational background effect on academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools students in Niger State?
3. What are the levels of parents' employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State?
4. What is the difference between Parents' income and Educational background on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State?
5. What is the level of Parents' Educational background and Employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State?

(Assessment of Parents Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement ... Suleiman, S. O. Et al., 2025)

6. What is the level of interactive effect between Parents' income, Educational background and level of Employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State?

Research Hypotheses

This will test the following empirical hypotheses:-

- H₀₁: There is no significant difference effect of parents' income on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
- H₀₂: There is no significant effect difference of parents' educational background on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
- H₀₃: There is no significant difference effect in parents' employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
- H₀₄: There is no significant difference effect of parents' income and educational background on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
- H₀₅: There is no significant difference effect of parents' educational background and levels of employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
- H₀₆: There is no significant difference in interactive effect of parents' income, educational background and employment on high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools student in Niger State.

Methodology

Research Design

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The research design for this study is ex-post-facto method in which groups with qualities that already exist are compared on dependent variables. Also known as “after the fact” research, an ex-post facto design is considered quasi-experimental because the subjects are not randomly assigned. They are grouped based on particular characteristics or traits. Assigning subjects to different groups is based on whichever variable is of interest to the researcher. Ex-post-facto research in education has permitted investigations of the effects of variables, such as home background, father’s absence, early experiences, disabilities, teacher competence and others that are beyond the control of educators. In some instances, ex-post-facto research has discovered relationships or raised questions that can later be investigated more systematically in well-controlled experimental studies.

Population of the Study

The population for this study consisted of over one hundred and fifty (150) secondary schools with an estimated numbers of three hundred and seventy three thousand, five hundred and twenty nine (373, 529) students in Niger State.

Sample Size

Based on the estimated population of this study, which is (n=373,529), in line with Baron and Kenny in Otuwa, (2019), 384 sample is adequate for a population of 1,000,000 and above. This is aligned with size believing that the six secondary schools will have more than such population. The study however, will administer a total of (537) questionnaire throughout the six secondary schools. The 40% increase in questionnaire is in line with non-response attitude of respondents (Alex 2022) and Nigeria’s attitudes of poor response rate to questionnaire (Murthy 2022). Out of over one hundred and fifty (150) secondary schools in Niger State; six (6) secondary schools are randomly selected according to the state geo-political zones.

Sampling Techniques

Multi stage cluster sampling is a more complex form of cluster sample, which contains two or more stages in sample selection. According to Pritha, (2021) Multi-stage sampling, or multistage cluster sampling, you draw a sample from a population using smaller groups (units) at each stage. It’s often used to collect data from a large, geographically spread group of people in a national survey. All the SS 111 students’ population of selected secondary schools in Niger State 2021/2020 was captured in

(Assessment of Parents Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement ... Suleiman, S. O. Et al., 2025)

this study, using Multi-stage sample. The first stage was using Cluster sampling technique to randomly select out fifteen (15) schools. This was done simply by writing the names of the whole schools each on separate sheets of paper, folded and a research assistant was asked to pick out a name after shaking the container where fifteen (15) different names were picked out. When it was opened, it contained the names of fifteen (15) schools. The second stage is also using the clustery sampling technique to select nine (9) schools out of the above fifteen (15) schools. The same process of clustery sampling was carried out picking nine (9) schools. The third stage is also using same the clustery sampling technique to select six (6) schools. Following the same clustery sampling technique. The fourth stage is to use stratified random sampling technique to select study sample size which from the population of the six (6) schools. This is done through the use of the students' class list from the exams office where every third name on the list was selected.

Data Collection Instrument

The data collection instruments using one adapted Questionnaire and examination generated scores, these are:-

Kuppuswamy Classification of Socio-Economic Status (Scale)

The Kuppuswamy Classification of Socio-economic Status was proposed by Kuppuswamy B. (1976). The adapted instrument was used to measures the SES of urban population. The instrument is to elicit for parents' socio-economic status data through the students. It's divided into three (3) sections based on the status of individuals, namely Section A Education, Section B Occupation and Section C Income of the household or family. Number of test items:- It contains 24 items shared within the three sections. Section A ten (10) items, section B seven (7) items and section C seven (7) items.

End of the Year Examination Scores

The end of the year examination scores is an internal assessment set and marked by the teachers. The scores obtained by examinees as results from a teacher made examination questions to mark the coverage of syllabus and end of the term or school

(Assessment of Parents Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement ... Suleiman, S. O. Et al., 2025)

calendar in secondary schools. In this study, EYES would be used to measure the students' academic achievement, through transforming the scores generated using Z scores statistical method. It's the means through which academic achievement will be measure in this study.

Pilot Testing

In this study, a pilot test would be carried out using the test re-test method. The purpose of conducting a pilot testing is to ascertain if respondents would encounter any difficulty in completing the instruments used in this study. The data collected are used to calculate the reliabilities value of the instruments with the aid of SPSS. Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient for each of the instrument will be shown. Test re-test reliability would be computed to examine the suitability of the instrument that is sought through a test re-test. Fifty (50) students from G.S.S Minna (Father "O" Connell) would be used in this testing.

Data Collection Procedure

A letter of introduction from the Department of Counselling Psychology would be presented at the office of the Principals of the selected secondary schools in Niger State. This is to grant the researcher access to collect the required data by administering the questionnaire to the selected respondents.

Data Analysis Procedure

The computation and organization of data will be done with SPSS software. However, the data will be transferred to and run on stata package for analysis. Hypotheses 1 and 2 will tested using ANOVA and Hypotheses 3 using regression analysis at the 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Result

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in effect of parents' income on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

(Assessment of Parents Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement ... Suleiman, S. O. Et al., 2025)

Table 1: One-way analysis of variance on the difference in the effect of Parents’ income on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Parent income	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	321.762	2	160.881	1.349	.261
Within Groups	44380.414	372	119.302		
Total	44702.176	374			

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A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to investigate potential difference in the effect of parents’ income on academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools students in Niger State. The analysis revealed that there was no statistically significant difference in academic achievement among secondary school students based on their parents' income levels, $F(2, 372) = 1.349$, $p = .261$. The between-groups sum of squares was 321.762, and the within-groups sum of squares was 44380.414, resulting in a total sum of squares of 44702.176. The mean square for between-groups was 160.881, and the mean square for within-groups was 119.302. These findings indicates that, at the 0.05 significance level, there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the effect of parents' income on academic achievement is not significantly different across high, moderate, and low income levels among secondary school students in Niger State.

H_{02} : There is no significant difference effect of parents’ educational background on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Table 2: One-way analysis of variance on the difference effect of Parents’ educational background on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Parent Educational Background	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	333.940	2	166.970	1.400	.248
Within Groups	44368.236	372	119.269		
Total	44702.176	374			

(Assessment of Parents Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement ... Suleiman, S. O. Et al., 2025)

Survey Report 2024

A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to determine the difference in the effect of parents' educational background effect on academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools students in Niger State. The analysis indicated that there was no statistically significant difference in academic achievement among secondary school students based on their parents' educational qualifications, $F(2, 372) = 1.400$, $p = .248$. The between-groups sum of squares was 333.940, and the within-groups sum of squares was 44368.236, resulting in a total sum of squares of 44702.176. The mean square for between-groups was 166.970, and the mean square for within-groups was 119.269. At the 0.05 significance level, the p-value of .248 suggests that there is no significant difference in academic achievement based on parents' educational qualification levels.

H_{03} : There is no significant difference effect of parents' employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Table 3: One-way analysis of variance on the difference effect of Parents' employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Parent Employment	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	333.830	2	166.970	1.300	.256
Within Groups	44259.328	372	118.279		
Total	44593.158	374			

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A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to investigate difference in the effect of parents' employment on academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools students in Niger State. The analysis revealed that there was no statistically significant difference in academic achievement among secondary school students based on their parents' employment levels, $F(2, 372) = 1.300$, $p = .256$. The between-groups sum of squares was 333.830, and the within-

(Assessment of Parents Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement ... Suleiman, S. O. Et al., 2025)

groups sum of squares was 44259.328, leading to a total sum of squares of 44593.158. The mean square for between-groups was 166.970, and the mean square for within-groups was 118.279. At the conventional 0.05 significance level, the p-value of .256 indicates that there is no significant difference in academic achievement among students with varying levels of parents' income.

H₀₄: There is no significant difference effect of parents' income and educational background on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Table 4: Multivariate Analysis of Variance on the effects of Parents' educational background and employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Effect		Value	F	Df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Sq
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.987	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
	Wilks' Lambda	.013	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
	Hotelling's Trace	74.354	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
	Roy's Largest Root	74.354	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
Qualification	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
Occupation	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
Qualification * Occupation	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000

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A multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was conducted to examine the effects of parents' educational background and employment on academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools students in Niger State. The analysis revealed significant effects for the Intercept, indicating that the model as a whole is statistically significant, with Wilks' showing substantial effect sizes (Pillai's Trace = .987, F = 3829.228, p < .001, partial eta squared = .987). However, the main

(Assessment of Parents Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement ... Suleiman, S. O. Et al., 2025)

effects of parents' educational background and employment, as well as their interaction, were found to be non-significant. Pillai's Trace for parents' educational background and employment, and the interaction term all yielded values of 0, indicating no significant effect on the academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools students in Niger State.

H₀₅: There is no significant difference effect of parents' educational background and employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Table 5: Multivariate Analysis of Variance on the effects of parents' income and educational background on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students

Effect		Value	F	df	Error	Sig.	Partial Eta
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.987	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
	Wilks' Lambda	.013	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
	Hotelling's Trace	74.354	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
	Roy's Largest Root	74.354	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
Income	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
Qualification	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
Income *Qualification	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000

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A multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was conducted to examine the effects of parents' income and educational background on academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools student in Niger State. C with Wilks' showing substantial effect sizes (Pillai's Trace = .987, F = 3829.228, p < .001, partial eta squared = .987). However, the main effects of parents' income and educational background, as well as their interaction, were found to be non-significant. Pillai's Trace for parents' income and educational background, and their interaction all yielded

(Assessment of Parents Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement ... Suleiman, S. O. Et al., 2025)

values of 0, indicating no significant effect on the academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools student in Niger State.

H₀₆: There is no significant interactive effect of parents' income, educational background and employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools student in Niger State.

Table 6: Multivariate analysis of variance on the effects of parents' income, educational background and employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students

Effect		Value	F	df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta S.
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.987	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
	Wilks' Lambda	.013	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
	Hotelling's Trace	74.354	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
	Roy's Largest Root	74.354	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
INCOME	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
QUALIFICATIO N	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
Occupation	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
Income * Qualification	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
Income * Occupation	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
Qualification * Occupation	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
Income * Qualification * Occupation	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000

Survey Report 2024

(Assessment of Parents Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement ... Suleiman, S. O. Et al., 2025)

A multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was conducted to examine the effects of parents' income, educational background and employment on academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools students in Niger State. The analysis revealed a significant effect for the Intercept, indicating that the model as a whole is statistically significant, with Wilks' showing substantial effect sizes (Pillai's Trace = .987, $F = 3829.228$, $p < .001$, partial eta squared = .987). However, the main effects of parents' income, educational background and employment, and all of their interactions were found to be non-significant. Pillai's Trace for parents' income, educational background and employment, and all interaction terms yielded values of 0, indicating no significant effect on the academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools student.

Discussion of Findings

From the analysis data, the study revealed that, at the 0.05 significance level, there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the effect of parents' income on academic achievement is not significantly different across high, moderate, and low income levels among secondary school students in Niger State. This is in line with study of Chioma, Bernedeth & Joseph (2017) who asserted that the students response on the effect of parental income on students' academic performance showed that greater academic achievement for a student was attained by those students from financially buoyant families (Mean(Mean \pm SD = 2.97 ± 0.88 , $X^2 = 11.991$, $P = 0.007$). However, 29.7% of the students strongly disagreed. This implies that parents with small income can only take care of a small percentage of a child's education, such as to pay school fees while the child is deprived of basic needs such as text books, school uniforms and sandals, which essence make the students' performance in school very low.

The study also revealed that the analysis indicated there was no statistically significant difference in academic achievement among secondary school students based on their parents' educational qualifications. This study is contrary to Amogne (2015) whose study revealed that parents' educational level has a strong association with academic performance of students. Students from educationally and better off families scored high results in their regional exams than their counterparts.

Furthermore, the analysis revealed that there was no statistically significant difference in academic achievement among secondary school students based on their parents'

(Assessment of Parents Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement ... Suleiman, S. O. Et al., 2025)

employment levels, this finding is at variance with Chioma, et al. (2017) opined that the study showed that parents' involvement in children schools activities matters most than their financial status in uplifting their children's academic performance in the school. Parental involvement in the education of their children not only improve their academic performance but also enhance other aspect of the lives of students such as motivation, improve behaviour, better communication skills as well as positive attitude toward school.

Also The analysis revealed significant effects for the Intercept, indicating that the model as a whole is statistically significant, with Wilks' showing substantial effect sizes (Pillai's Trace = .987, $F = 3829.228$, $p < .001$, partial eta squared = .987). This finding is in line with Musangu and Ghazali (2017) whose study findings revealed a positive relationship between all the three variables of socio-economic status and academic performance of Secondary School students in the Western Province of the Republic of Zambia. Hence, parents' income carried strong influence on the academic performance of Secondary School students (beta =0.879). The effect of parents' level of education on the academic performance was second (beta =0.758) while occupation had the least influence (beta=0.65).

Furthermore, the analysis of the finding revealed a significant effect for the Intercept, indicating that the model as a whole is statistically significant, with Wilks' showing substantial effect sizes (Pillai's Trace = .987, $F = 3829.228$, $p < .001$, partial eta squared = .987). However, the main effects of parents' income and educational background, as well as their interaction, were found to be non-significant. This finding of this study also contradicted the study by Masangu and Ghazali (2017) and Amogne (2015). The result of the analysis revealed that the socio-economic status of parents (particularly affects their educational level and occupational status) has a strong association with the academic performance of students. Students from educationally and better of this off families scored higher results in their regional examination than their counterparts

Lastly, the study also The analysis revealed a significant effect for the Intercept, indicating that the model as a whole is statistically significant, with Wilks' showing substantial effect sizes (Pillai's Trace = .987, $F = 3829.228$, $p < .001$, partial eta squared = .987). However, the main effects of parents' income, educational background and employment, and all of their interactions were found to be non-significant. This finding also contradicted the study finding by Ovansa (2015 drawn

(Assessment of Parents Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement ... Suleiman, S. O. Et al., 2025)

from the analysis that parents' socio-economic status influences the academic performance of students. this explained why it was recommended that government should introduce scholarship scheme to assist less privilege students and provide basic social amenities in public schools.

Conclusion

The findings of this current investigation revealed that parents' socio-economic status (finance) have a significant effect on the academic achievement of secondary schools students in Niger State.

Recommendations

It has been established from the study that Parents socio-economic status plays an important role influencing secondary school students' academic achievement. Therefore:

1. Parents should support the educational pursuit of their children both financially, academically, and experience wise etc.
2. Government should ensure that qualify teachers were sent to rural areas to teach in secondary schools.
3. Scholarship assistance can be initiated in secondary schools to assist the good and less privilege students achieve their educational dreams.
4. Parents should spend quality times with student to assist them with school work
5. Parents should ensure that school needs such as recommended text books, uniforms and school fees are provided and paid as at when due.
6. Parents can provide the students with extramural teacher to teach them at home during weeks and vacations

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(Assessment of Parents Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement ... Suleiman, S. O. Et al., 2025)

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